

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Machine-learning based spatiotemporal prediction of soil moisture in a grassland hillslope

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Abstract

Soil moisture (SM) plays a significant role in the earth's water balance and in optimizing land management practices. However, SM at the field scale is difficult to map from available point measurements due to the inherent heterogeneity of soil and terrain properties and temporal dynamics of weather conditions. In this study, we explored the potential of four machine learning (ML) methods (random forest, gradient boosted regression trees, support vector regression, and neural networks) to predict SM in a grassland hillslope in space and time using auxiliary variables on soil and terrain properties and weather conditions. For training and testing the ML models, we used SM point measurements obtained by a sensor network. Performance metrics varied between the ML methods and the training-test data split ($R^2 = 0.48$ – 0.69 , root-mean-square error [RMSE] = 0.06 – 0.10). Random forests and gradient-boosted regression trees turned out to be promising and easy to parametrize as first choices to explore the potential of ML techniques. The day of the year emerged as an important feature to predict SM across models and can thus serve as a proxy for seasonal hydroclimatic variability. To enable the transfer of the application to other contexts or sites, we provide the modeling workflow as an open-source computational Python module.

Abbreviations: CV, cross-validation; GBRT, gradient boosted regression trees; MAE, mean absolute error; ML, machine learning; NN, neural network; R^2 , coefficient of determination; RF, random forest; RMSE, root-mean-square error; SM, soil moisture; STU, soil topographic unit; SVM, support vector machines; SVR, support vector regression.

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Plain Language Summary

Soil moisture is crucial for water balance and land management but is hard to predict due to soil and terrain variability. We tested four machine learning (ML) models—Random Forest, Gradient Boosted Trees, Support Vector Regression, and Neural Networks—to predict soil moisture in a grassland hillslope using soil, terrain, and weather data. Our results showed that Random Forest and Gradient Boosted Trees performed best, with model accuracy varying based on how the data set was splitted into training and test data. The day of the year was a key predictor, reflecting seasonal weather and moisture changes. To support broader applications, we provide our ML workflow as an open-source Python module for use in other studies and locations.

1 | INTRODUCTION

Soil moisture (SM) is a crucial component controlling the multi-functionality of the soil system (hydrology and biogeochemistry) and thus an important physical indicator for soil health. Therefore, information on SM is required by a variety of stakeholders, particularly in science and the agricultural sector (Seneviratne et al., 2010; Vereecken et al., 2022). For instance, monitoring SM can help to optimize land management practices, especially to improve crop yield (Dai et al., 2011; Gao et al., 2014).

The assessment of SM is challenging despite the existence of several measurement and monitoring methods such as remote sensing, sample-based laboratory measurements, and in situ sensors. SM is highly heterogeneous across spatiotemporal scales. This heterogeneity arises from various factors such as the variability in climate, topography, and vegetation at larger scales but also from the large variety of soil types, pore sizes within soils, and biogeochemical processes as well as the availability of macropores at smaller scales (Fatichi et al., 2015; Teuling, 2005; Teuling et al., 2007). Remote sensing from airborne vehicles and satellites can provide spatial SM data or data along trajectories (Babaeian et al., 2021; Kisekka et al., 2022). Nevertheless, remote sensing is still limited to coarse spatial ($>1000\text{ m}^2$) and temporal (days) resolution, a penetration depth of a few centimeters (Wagner et al., 2007) and can be distorted by interferences with vegetation and terrain patterns (e.g., Bogena et al., 2015). Proximal (ground-based) sensing techniques such as microwave radiometry and cosmic ray sensing have gained attention as they can provide SM estimates at intermediate scales ($<1000\text{ m}$) up to a depth of 0.8 m (Schrön et al., 2018). For instance, cosmic ray sensing can observe temporal variations in SM at the area around the sensor mount location or spatial variations when mounted on a ground-based vehicle. Recent technological advancements are, for instance, the application of a rail-based cosmic ray sensing

device that can observe spatiotemporal SM variations along railroad networks (Altdorf et al., 2023) as well as the testing of cosmic ray sensor clusters across an agricultural research site (Heistermann et al., 2023). Still, more research is required in order to reduce measurement errors (Andreasen et al., 2023), especially at high temporal resolutions (Altdorf et al., 2023). Moreover, cosmic ray measurement devices are relatively expensive, and thus, this type of spatial or trajectory data is not largely available. In contrast, in situ SM sensors are inexpensive and more widely available; however, they provide only point measurements. Thus, monitoring SM at the field scale ($10\text{--}1000\text{ m}^2$) relevant to land management is cumbersome and insufficiently satisfied by prevailing instrumentation (Dobriyal et al., 2012). Additionally, maintaining a dense network of in situ SM sensors becomes expensive and is prone to malfunction (Martini et al., 2015).

There are several approaches to map or predict SM at the field scale from point measurements, each with its individual challenge. For example, interpolations of point measurements with geometric methods such as inverse-distance weighting are straightforward to apply but at the same time neglect underlying relationships and processes in the soil system and, thus, suffer from low accuracy (J. Li & Heap, 2014). Kriging (a.k.a. Gaussian Process Regression) is a conventional geostatistical interpolation method that uses the spatial autocorrelation of the SM across the area of interest for prediction (Takagi & Lin, 2012; Yao et al., 2013). Here, difficulties can arise in estimating the spatial autocorrelation function from observations, especially when the terrain is highly heterogeneous. Last, process-based models can serve to predict SM based on water balance and governing flow equations (Chen et al., 2014; Kalma et al., 1995). Still, these models require extensive parametrization and face high uncertainties related to model assumptions and equifinality in the parameters.

Recently, machine learning (ML) methods gained attention for spatial modeling of soil properties (Hengl et al., 2018; Padarian et al., 2020) and SM (e.g., Babaeian et al., 2021;

Cai et al., 2019; Kisekka et al., 2022; Q. Li et al., 2022; Nguyen et al., 2022; Oliveira et al., 2021; Schröter et al., 2015; Wei et al., 2019; Xie et al., 2020; Zeng et al., 2019; Dega et al., 2023). ML methods can learn correlations between SM and auxiliary data on the environment and spatiotemporal SM patterns without assumptions or parametrization of complex underlying processes and thus represent a promising prediction alternative. For instance, Schröter et al. (2015) estimated field-scale SM patterns with a clustering approach. Xie et al. (2020) evaluated several ML methods using terrain and soil data for spatial prediction of SM at a large scale (>10,000 km²). Cai et al. (2019) and Q. Li et al. (2022) evaluated neural network (NN) models (deep learning and long short-term memory NN models) for temporal prediction of SM. Zeng et al. (2019) investigated spatiotemporal prediction of SM at a scale of 100–1000 km² using random forest (RF) models regressing on terrain, climate, and remote sensing data. Oliveira et al. (2021) compared several popular ML methods (including NN, RF, and support vector regression [SVR]) to predict SM at the field scale in the Atlantic Forest across space and time. Babaeian et al. (2021) report the use of NN, RF, and gradient boosted regression trees (GBRT) for spatiotemporal prediction of field-scale SM in an experimental agricultural field from ground-based and remotely sensed soil property data as well as, additionally, from in situ SM data. Kisekka et al. (2022) applied an RF model to estimate root zone SM in an irrigated vineyard from remote sensing, soil property, terrain, and climate data. Another popular ML method that has already been successfully applied to GBRT for downscaling remote sensing SM products (Wei et al., 2019) is GBRT. In addition, Nguyen et al. (2022) used a gradient boosting method (among others) to predict near-surface field-scale SM using satellite data across Western Australia. Recently, Dega et al. (2023) applied a Monte Carlo approach in regression RFs to regionalize SM and estimate the impact of uncertainties in the data on the final predictions. This shows that the soil hydrology and remote sensing community is already exploring ML for SM prediction. However, there are several issues that are still insufficiently addressed when applying ML (1) the need for more studies comparing several ML methods, (2) the need for further measures and methods for model interpretation, and (3) the need to ensure reproducibility in ML workflows.

The potential of ML strongly depends on the ML methods applied and on the type and quality of the input data (Domingos, 2012). Regarding SM, model prediction performance and representativeness depend on the type and scale of the study site, the method of SM quantification (e.g., in situ sensors, gravimetric measurements from soil cores), the spatial support of the sensor (e.g., a few cubic centimeters of soil to more than 10 ha down to about 20–40 cm [cosmic ray neutron sensors], Schrön et al., 2018) as well as the temporal resolution of measured SM data. Besides this, the environmental

Core Ideas

- Soil moisture was predicted from terrain, soil, and weather data.
- Four different machine-learning methods were comparatively evaluated.
- Tree-based models turned out to be the best performing and easy to set up.
- The choice of the training and test data affects prediction performance.
- A reproducible workflow is provided as a Python software module.

features (auxiliary data) chosen as predictors are substantial. Across the previously cited literature, the employed ML methods, study scales (hillslope, catchment, basin), prediction goals (spatial, temporal, spatiotemporal), SM quantification methods, auxiliary data sources (in situ, soil core analysis, remote sensing), and predictive performance differ. From the listed studies, NN and tree-based methods such as RF and GBRT appear to be the most often applied and promising ML methods. Comparative studies that evaluate these methods (among others) under the same conditions (study site, predictor variables) are yet few (Babaeian et al., 2021; Oliveira et al., 2021; Nguyen et al., 2022). However, the data-driven nature of ML methods hampers comparisons between individual ML methods under different conditions, that is, different study areas. Further studies that compare NN and RF across a range of sites and conditions are required in order to sufficiently evaluate their suitability as SM prediction tools.

Moreover, the complexity of ML methods complicates model interpretation and the identification of relevant environmental drivers in the input data (Reichstein et al., 2019). Here, measures to quantitatively assess relevant input data (e.g., feature importance or feature weights analysis) are required. Such measures are lacking in ML applications in soil science as concluded in a review by Padarian et al. (2020), and have only been recently considered (Babaeian et al., 2021; Kisekka et al., 2022; Q. Li et al., 2022; Nguyen et al., 2022; Oliveira et al., 2021; Zeng et al., 2019). An insufficient evaluation of feature importance limits the interpretability of ML-based SM prediction and of data requirements. Without such an adequate identification and consideration of relevant predictors, a wider application of ML and its transfer into practice can be limited.

The ML modeling workflow itself can be complicated as it requires extensive action on data preprocessing (e.g., extraction of predictor variables (features) from raw input data, quality controls, scaling, partitioning into training and test sets), model execution (model (hyper) parameter

optimization with cross-validation (CV), feature importance), model and results analysis (e.g., computation of performance metrics across time or spatial subsets), and interpretation (Goodfellow et al., 2016; Reichstein et al., 2019). Therefore, ensuring transparency and reproducibility of SM prediction results and the transfer of developed prediction methods onto other sites, contexts, or into practice requires a transparent documentation of the corresponding computational workflow (e.g., open-source code repositories, data processing and modeling protocols, supplementary information, publishing (raw) datasets) (Brunsdon & Comber, 2021). In general, reproducibility in hydrological research was estimated to be below 7% only a few years back (Stagge et al., 2019). As far as the authors are aware, only Q. Li et al. (2022) provided a full repository including the code and data that allows to easily reproduce and test the employed models, although code-based scientific tools are commonly used. For instance, in many studies, it is unclear how the SM data have been partitioned into training and test sets. Whether SM data from different depths at the same location or from the same sensor (same depth and location) but at different times end up in either the training or test set or in both sets is not always clear from the methodological description. Xie et al. (2020) report that prediction performance varied across depth-specific subsets of SM data from the same site, suggesting that the method by which SM data are partitioned into training and test sets affects prediction performance. This shows that there is a substantial gap in methodological reporting and a need for increasing the reproducibility and consistency in SM prediction studies. This is especially crucial to transfer scientific results into tools for practitioners in agriculture, forestry, and ecosystem management.

To address the mentioned knowledge gap on comparative results and the methodological gaps on input data relevance and reproducibility, we conducted a comparative study on spatiotemporal prediction of field-scale SM with ML. For this, we evaluated the performance of RF and NN among support vector machine (SVM) and GBRT to predict in situ SM observations. The observations were obtained from a sensor network across a grassland hillslope in a small agricultural field site in central Germany. To the best of our knowledge, such a comparative study setting has not been evaluated yet but will be beneficial to investigate the suitability of ML-based SM prediction. Further, we conducted measures to evaluate input data relevance and data partitioning (into training and test sets) in order to further interpret our models. To ensure reproducibility of our workflow, we provide all input data and the corresponding code as a Python software module alongside this article.

The specific objectives of this study are to (1) compare the performance of four different ML methods (RF, GBRT, SVR, and NN) to predict SM across space and time from in situ, terrain, soil, and climate data, (2) assess the importance of

input data partitioning into training and test sets, (3) assess the importance of considered features, (4) predict SM maps in order to interpret the models, (5) discuss our map predictions and model handling, and (6) provide a Python software module with a reproducible workflow. The results of this study, our developed module, and the transparent documentation will assist further research on SM prediction to choose the best-suited ML methods and to develop a reproducible workflow. Moreover, this study will be beneficial to build practical SM prediction tools for agriculture, forestry, landscaping, and ecosystem management.

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Study area and available datasets

The studied hillslope section is part of the Schäfertal catchment (here referred to as “study site”; see Figure 1). The Schäfertal is a small agricultural catchment (1.44 km²) situated in the lower Harz Mountains in Central Germany and part of the Terrestrial Environmental Observatories (TERENO) Harz/Central German Lowland Observatory (Zacharias et al., 2011). Cropland primarily characterizes the slopes in the upper region of the catchment, while the studied hillslope section (approximately 250 m by 80 m) is covered by grassland being cut once to twice a year (Martini et al., 2015). The hillslope is divided by the creek Schäferbach into a northern and southern slope. In the studied section, elevation decreases from approximately 403 m in the upper part of the northern slope down to 387 m at the bottom land (average angle 6°), where the Schäferbach is located. From the bottomland, elevation increases again to 395 m at the southern slope at an average angle of 7° (Figure 1). The hillslope section can be classified into four different soil topographic units (STUs, units of similar pedological description). The dominant soil types are silty loam Cambisols and Luvisols on the slopes and Gleysols with finer materials in the valley bottom (Martini et al., 2015; Ollesch et al., 2005). The climate in the Schäfertal catchment is subcontinental with a mean annual air temperature of 6.9°C and a minimum temperature of approximately –24°C. It receives approximately 655 mm of precipitation per year (based on 1968–2013, Martini et al., 2015) including a large part as snow during the winter seasons.

2.1.1 | Target variable—Soil moisture measurements

SM data over 14 months (September 15, 2012 till November 14, 2013) were acquired by Martini et al. (2015) using a hybrid wireless sensor network in the hillslope (SoilNet (soil moisture sensor network in TERENO), Bogena et al., 2010).

FIGURE 1 Study area with sensor locations (top, left) and daily mean soil moisture averaged over sensors for each depth with interquartile range (bottom, right). Coordinate Reference System: Gauss Kruger Zone 4 (EPSG:3397).

The sensor network includes 40 sampling points, identified using conditional Latin hypercube sampling of geophysical data (Martini et al., 2015). At each of the 40 sampling points (boxes), six sensors measured SM at three soil depths (two sensors for each depth: 0.05, 0.25, and 0.50 m; see Martini et al. [2015] for more details). For each sensor, daily mean SM values were obtained from hourly SM measurements, resulting in a maximum of 240 SM sensor values per day (Martini et al., 2015). For 425 days, 88,867 data points were obtained, from which entries without numeric values have been removed and three out of the 40 boxes delivered no data. The processed SM data are depicted as averages in Figure 1 and for each sensor and box in Figure S1.

2.1.2 | Features—Spatial auxiliary data

We used point-based soil data from Martini et al. (2015). These data include (a) soil texture data (sand, silt, and clay content) at each SM sampling point and sensor depth and (b) porosity data for each layer of the four STUs. Martini et al.

(2015) calculated porosity based on the maximum observed saturation. We then interpolated the point-based soil texture and porosity data with ordinary kriging onto a raster (1 m × 1 m resolution) of the study site for the intended prediction of SM maps (Section S1; Figure S2–S8; Table S1).

A digital elevation model from airborne laser scanning (light detection and ranging [LIDAR]) with a resolution of 1 m (Schröter et al., 2015) was used to obtain the elevation, the slope, the aspect (i.e., the orientation of the slope), and the topographic wetness index (the topographic tendency of a location to be wet according to Beven & Kirkby, 1979) at the sampling points (Figure S12; Table S2).

2.1.3 | Features—Temporal auxiliary data

The climatic conditions were assumed to be equal across the entire study site. Daily total precipitation and hourly values of air temperature were acquired from a hydro-meteorological station located approximately 100 m west of the study area (DWD, Deutscher Wetterdienst, 2024; Martini et al., 2015).

TABLE 1 Set of auxiliary variables (features) used for the prediction of soil moisture in the machine learning models.

Category	Feature	Unit	Resolution	Reference	Mean	Std.	CV
Time	Date as integer ^a		Daily		213.0	122.8	0.57
	Day of the year sine		Daily		-0.13	0.73	-5.69
	Day of the year cosine		Daily		0.03	0.67	18.73
Geometry	x coordinate (Easting)				641993.3	17.3	0.00
	y coordinate (Northing)				572466.5	73.1	0.00
	Sensor depth (= z coordinate)	m			0.27	0.18	0.69
Topography	Elevation	m	1 m	DEM (Schröter et al., 2015)	394.63	4.17	0.01
	Slope	°			5.06	2.03	0.40
	Aspect sin				0.31	0.21	0.69
	Aspect cos				-0.33	0.98	-2.64
	Topographic wetness index				6.06	3.44	0.57
Weather	Precipitation	mm	Daily	(Martini et al., 2015)	1.76	4.60	2.62
	Potential evapotranspiration	mm	Daily	(Martini et al., 2015)	1.27	1.27	0.99
	Air temperature	°C	Daily, (hourly averages)	(DWD, Deutscher Wetterdienst, 2024)	7.12	7.73	1.09
Soil property	Silt content	% ^b	For each point at each soil depth at each raster point (interpolated), for each soil depth	(Martini et al., 2015) for Ordinary kriging for maps (see Section 2.1.2)	68.7	10.4	0.15
	Clay content	% ^b			15.7	4.9	0.31
	Sand content	% ^b			15.6	10.9	0.70
	Porosity	% ^b			0.55	0.11	0.20

Abbreviations: CV, cross-validation; DEM, digital elevation model; STU, soil topographic unit.

^aStarting with 1 for September 16, 2012 till 425 for November 14, 2013.

^bBy weight.

Daily potential evapotranspiration was calculated with the combination method after Penman (1948) (Figure S9). Julian days were transformed by sine and cosine. The sine of the Julian days represents values of variables that are equal in winter and summer and opposite in spring and autumn; the cosine represents opposite values in winter and summer and similar values in spring and autumn (e.g., air temperature) (Table 1).

2.2 | Application of machine-learning methods

2.2.1 | Machine-learning methods

Four different ML methods were applied and compared for their prediction performance: (i) RFs, (ii) GBRT, (iii) SVR, and (iv) NNs.

The ML methods differed in their architecture and methodology. RF employs an ensemble of decision trees that differ in their structures, for example, due to bootstrapping of the samples (i.e., different random subsets). In a decision tree, each node (i.e., a decision) divides the data into two sets based

on a random subset of the features in order to minimize the model error. This process is repeated several times to construct a decision tree. Finally, predictions of the target variable correspond to the average over the individual trees, a method called bagging. In contrast, GBRT builds a series of decision trees with each new tree predicting the residuals of the previous step. This sequential process to minimize the overall prediction residuals is called boosting. Finally, predictions correspond to the initial prediction of the target variable (e.g., mean value) corrected by the sum of all predicted residuals of the individual trees multiplied by the predefined learning rate. SVR is based on an SVM (Cortes & Vapnik, 1995) wherein a hyperplane describing the multivariate data is identified. This hyperplane is optimized by minimizing the weights associated with the features while limiting the error to be within a user-defined threshold. An NN consists of multiple layers where each layer is composed of several nodes (or neurons). The input layer has as many nodes as the parameters provided to the model, while the output layer has as many nodes as possible outputs. Input and output layers are connected via hidden layers, which can vary in number and size depending on the complexity of the network (Dave & Dutta, 2014). The supervised learning algorithm iteratively learns a nonlinear

FIGURE 2 Workflow for a spatiotemporal soil moisture (SM) prediction with a single machine learning (ML) method. The rectangle depicts the current functionality of the Python software module.

function that connects the input layer with the output layer based on learned weights.

2.2.2 | Modeling workflow

For each ML model, the input data comprising the described SM and auxiliary data (features, Table 1) were split into a dataset for training (fitting; 80% of the data) and testing (evaluating; 20% of the data) the models in a way that data at the same location (SM sensor position and depth) were moved into either the training or test set (Figure 2). In other words, the split into training and test datasets (training-test split) was done by randomly assigning SM (and corresponding auxiliary) data at a specific location to either the training or test set. To evaluate potential effects of the random splitting, we created five different training-test splits (i.e., repetitions) by changing the “seed” parameter, which controls a random split

and ensures its reproducibility (Figure S11). The datasets of a specific training-test split were scaled by subtracting the mean values and dividing through standard deviation of the respective training set. The models were then separately trained on the same training datasets. For training, the model parameters (i.e., hyperparameters) were optimized in an automatic procedure. This procedure included fivefold CV with random search across the range of model parameters. For the fivefold CV, the training data were split into five subsets (folds) based on the sensor locations (same fashion as done for splitting the entire dataset into a training and test set described above). To say, for each subset, data from a sensor at a particular location in the training set were included in either the part for fitting (tuning) the hyperparameters or for their validation. For each training-test split, model performances were assessed by key performance metrics (coefficient of determination [R^2], root-mean-square error [RMSE], and mean absolute error [MAE], see Section 2.2.4) of the

corresponding training and test datasets. The importance of individual auxiliary variables was evaluated by computing the change in R^2 of a model where a certain auxiliary variable was or was not included due to permutation (see Section 2.2.5). As the last step, SM maps were predicted using the best performing model for each ML method (see Section 2.2.6). Detailed information on the workflow and model hyper parameters are given in Section S3.2 and Tables S3–S6.

2.2.3 | Python software module

To standardize our modeling, ensure its reproducibility, and allow its application or adaptation to other SM prediction/modeling contexts, we developed our modeling workflow as a module for the Python programming language. The module's generic design allows a user to set up and run ML models as employed in this study for SM predictions with consistent commands as a script or interactively from a Python command line. The functionality includes the input data preprocessing, model fitting (training), performance evaluation, and SM prediction including visualization capabilities (Figure 2). The ML models used in the module are based on the Python package scikit-learn (Pedregosa et al., 2011). For a detailed description of our module, see Section S3.1 and Figure S13. The module is freely available on GitHub (<https://github.com/timohouben/sm-module>) and is referenced via Zenodo (Houben, Boog, et al., 2025).

2.2.4 | Performance evaluation

To evaluate the model performance, we calculated the following metrics: the MAE, the R^2 (also referred to as the Nash–Sutcliffe model efficiency coefficient, Chen et al., 2014; Nash & Sutcliffe, 1970), and the RMSE. See Section S3.3 for details.

2.2.5 | Feature importance

To derive the features deemed important for the predictions of each ML model, permutation feature importance was applied as implemented in the scikit-learn package and usable from within our SM module. The importance was quantified by computing the decrease in model performance in terms of the R^2 when the respective feature is randomly shuffled:

$$i_j = R_{\text{base}}^2 - \frac{1}{N} \sum_n R_{n,j}^2 \quad (1)$$

where i_j is the computed importance of feature j , R_{base}^2 is the R^2 of the model based on the actual input data, $R_{n,j}^2$ is

the model performance associated with input data with a randomly shuffled feature j , and N is the number of shuffling repetitions (here, $N = 15$). Essentially, the feature importance i_j is the reduction in model performance when artificially breaking the relationship between the feature j and the target variable by shuffling. Thus, the higher the value of i_j , the higher the importance of feature j for model performance. Feature importance was computed for both training and test datasets.

2.2.6 | Soil moisture map predictions

We used the trained models to generate SM predictions across a raster of the entire study site for a wet (February 16, 2013, spring) and a dry (July 16, 2013, summer) state. For each raster cell, we used auxiliary data (features) as described in Table 1 and in Sections 2.1.2 and 2.1.3 as input data to the models.

3 | RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 | Spatiotemporal prediction performance

Four different ML methods were trained and evaluated for five different spatial training-test splits of the study site each (in total, 20 trained models). In general, prediction performance differed with both the ML method and the split into training and test data. The model performances on the test dataset reached a minimum MAE of 0.040 m³/m³ for RF, 0.056 m³/m³ for NN, 0.047 m³/m³ for GBRT, and 0.053 m³/m³ for SVR. However, the MAE and RMSE varied with the training-test split as well as the ML method (Figure 3). The highest R^2 was observed mostly for training-test splits 1 and 5 for GBRT (0.60 and 0.69) and RF (~0.66) and for NN (0.48 and 0.51); see Figure 3. In contrast, for SVR, the R^2 was highest for training-test splits 1 and 2 (0.53 and 0.48). For all models, training performances exceeded test performances potentially hinting toward overfitting (Figure S14), although we optimized and controlled model complexity by applying hyperparameter tuning with CV to reduce overfitting. The differences between training and test performances varied across the four applied ML methods. Interestingly, the models with simpler model structures (RF, GRBT) tended to have higher differences between training and test performance while still reaching the highest test performances.

Exploring spatial variation in performance metrics (specifically, depth-wise), the RMSE also varied with the depth of prediction (Figure 3d). Temporally, the variation of the RMSE was higher in shallower depths, while at depth 0.5 m it was more homogenous with only small variations across seasons. In contrast, the absolute values of the RMSE over time

FIGURE 3 Performance statistics on the test dataset across the four machine learning (ML) methods and different training-test splits. The training-test splits differed in the random seed used for splitting the entire dataset (Figure S11). Panels (a), (b), and (c) display R^2 score, root-mean-square error (RMSE), and mean absolute error (MAE), respectively, for each training-test split aggregated across space and time. Panel (d) displays RMSE varying with time and depth. GBRT, gradient boosted regression trees; NN, neural network; RF, random forest; SVR, support vector regression.

were lower at a depth of 0.05 m compared to 0.50 m. The RMSE was relatively high during spring, strongly decreasing in summer for RF and GBRT before rising again in autumn (Figure 3d) with MAE following similar trends (Figure S16). Across the ML methods, SVR was the least affected by the training-test split of the dataset (R^2 varied between 0.40 and 0.53) and, hence, it was the most robust.

In general, obtained performance statistics are in range with other studies on spatial, temporal, and spatiotemporal SM prediction applying kriging methods (Takagi & Lin, 2012; Yao et al., 2013) and process-based models (Chen et al., 2014) as well as studies using ML methods (Q. Li et al., 2022; Schröter et al., 2015; Xie et al., 2020; Zeng et al., 2019). For instance, Yao et al. (2013) identified regression kriging as superior to ordinary kriging, linear regression, and

inverse distance weighting to interpolate SM across a 2 km² wide catchment. In their study, the RMSE of SM predictions by regression kriging across different data subsets is approximately 0.01–0.02 m³/m³ lower than for inverse distance weighting but these differences vanish when predictions by regression kriging are compared to predictions by multiple linear regression. Meanwhile, using process-based models, Chen et al. (2014) reported a similar R^2 of SM prediction yet required an extensive calibration effort to achieve this. This shows the advantage of data-driven approaches for prediction, as these do not require extensive calibration compared to process-based models. Q. Li et al. (2022), Takagi and Lin (2012), Yao et al. (2013), and Xie et al. (2020) reported that differences in performance metrics between ML methods on the same data subsets lie in the range of differences

in performance metrics of individual models across multiple data subsets. Despite this, the same authors report that individual ML methods achieve better average performance metrics (e.g., higher R^2 and lower RMSE) than others. This is in line with our findings on differences between training-test data splits and ML methods. For instance, Q. Li et al. (2022) evaluated several ML methods (a NN-based long short-term memory model as well as RF and SVR) for temporal SM prediction of FLUXNET sites considering lagged SM and climatic conditions. In their study, RF and SVR exhibited relatively similar performances on several datasets but were generally outperformed by the long short-term memory model. Taking our results and those of the studies by Q. Li et al. (2022), Takagi and Lin (2012), Yao et al. (2013), and Xie et al. (2020) into account, the performance of prediction models will most probably vary for specific datasets. The specifics can be due to data sampled at different sites, soil depths, or even predictions for different points in time.

Additionally, performance varies by how the datasets were split, as shown by the effects of different random training-test splits on model performance (Figure 3). Among the methods, the different splits led to a range of 0.13–0.24 in R^2 (with maximum variation for GBRT), an average range of 0.03 in the RMSE (with maximum variation for RF) and an average range of 0.024 in the MAE (with maximum variation for RF) (Figure 3). Defining the random seed ensured the reproducibility of randomly splitting the data. Since the splitting of the dataset is carried out randomly, some training-test splits may result in imbalanced datasets wherein the training data may not be representative of the complete observation range. This is of concern especially when the number of SM observation locations is low and when SM observations between locations differ strongly (Zeng et al., 2019; Figures S1 and S11). The latter can be expected due to the high degree of heterogeneity in soil processes arising from the spatial variability of, for example, soil textures. Point measurements often fail to fully capture this complexity, resulting in soil processes appearing random (Martini et al., 2015; Western et al., 1999). Our training datasets contain approximately 30 locations for each split, while approximately eight locations were assigned to the test dataset. Thus, spatial splitting (based on locations) can result in different SM ranges in the training and test sets, which can reduce the prediction performance. Investigating different splits is thus indispensable to avoid bias in the model evaluation regarding spatial prediction abilities.

Scatterplots of predicted versus observed SM looked relatively similar across the four ML methods (Figure 4) as well as the relative errors (Figure S17); that is, across methods, largest absolute differences occurred mainly for extreme SM values (i.e., very low [$SM < 0.1$] and very high [$SM > 0.6$] values) and largest relative differences for small SM values. The difficulty of predicting extreme SM can partly be caused by the imbalances in the training and test dataset as discussed

above and the generally smaller proportion of observations for the extreme SM values. Similar effects have been observed in comparable studies using RF (Zeng et al., 2019) and NN (Cai et al., 2019). Nevertheless, higher predictability of low SM in summer was observed for RF and GBRT (Figure 3d; Figure S16). This could be related to a high spatial coherence during consistently dry conditions across locations, especially at the shallow depth of 0.05 m (Figure 1; Martini et al., 2017) and a strong vertical SM gradient (Figure 1).

3.2 | Feature importance

The general patterns of feature importance were similar between training and test data for each ML method (Figure 5). This indicates that training and test performances are similarly sensitive to the features suggesting negligible overfitting to irrelevant features and increasing confidence in their predictive ability.

Similarly, feature importance patterns coarsely matched between individual models despite differences in absolute importance values. Across models, *sine of the Day of the year* was consistently the most important predictor (0.36–1.26 for test sets), followed by the *cosine of the Day of the year* (0.09–0.27 for test sets), the *Date as Integer* in the case of RF (0.09–1.0 for the test sets), the *Depth of the sensor* (0.09–0.27 for test sets), and *Soil Porosity*, especially for NN (0.05–0.36 for test sets). Further, *Elevation* turned out to be an important feature for RF, GBRT, and NN (0.10–0.35 for the test sets). Interestingly, the climatic variables *Air Temperature*, *Precipitation*, and *Evapotranspiration* (0.01–0.05 for the test sets across all models) showed only minor importance for the model performance, although their variabilities in the dataset are relatively high compared to the variability of *Soil Porosity*, *Elevation*, and *Depth of the sensor*. In contrast, a high variability in *cosine of the Day of the year* and *sine of the Day of the year* corresponds to the high importance of these features. Additionally, correlations of SM with predictors do not directly translate into high feature importance. For instance, *Depth of Sensor* has a low correlation with SM (Figure S10) but a high feature importance. Such contradictions just express how ML models are able to find complex nonlinear relationships that are not obvious at first sight.

Both the *sine* and the *cosine of the Day of the year* express seasonal patterns and thus are linked to the strong seasonal variations of SM (Figure 1; Figure S10). The greater importance of the *sine of the Day of the year* compared to the *cosine* could be due to the fact that its opposite values in March and September reflect a high SM in March and a low SM in August and September, whereas the *cosine* has the same function values in March and September. This importance is also reflected in higher correlation between *sine of the Day of the year* and SM observations compared to the *cosine* (Figure S10). The

FIGURE 4 Model predictions versus observations of daily mean soil moisture (SM) across machine learning (ML) methods (test data of training-test split 5 with 22,066 samples). The dark red line shows the 1:1 ratio between predictions and observations. GBRT, gradient boosted regression trees; NN, neural network; RF, random forest; SVR, support vector regression.

sine and cosine functions are phase-shifted by one quarter of the year, which might allow the models to learn different time lags of seasonal drivers affecting the temporal variability of SM. Thus, the *Day of the year* emerged as a proxy for seasonal hydroclimatic variability with different seasonal shifts depending on the *sine* or *cosine* function, respectively.

The *Depth of the Sensor* explains the vertical seasonal differences in SM resulting from attenuation of the superficial hydroclimatic forcing at the atmosphere–soil interface. These different degrees of attenuation can clearly be seen in the SM observations (Figure 1). Similarly, *Soil Porosity* was important for RF (0.06–0.07 for the test sets), GBRT (0.11–0.12 for the test sets), and NN (0.33–0.3 for the test sets) models, as its spatial and depth gradient additionally explains SM variations across soil depth (Figure S8b).

Although the climatic variables did not turn out to be important predictors across models, they are in the end the drivers for temporal variability in SM. *Air temperature* evolves seasonally in relation to the variation in solar radiation transferring into the soil where the temperature gets increas-

ingly attenuated and delayed along the soil depth profile. The temperature is linked to evapotranspiration and thus vertical water transport and release of water to the atmosphere. Precipitation controls the water input to the soil, where its forcing signal is, however, aggregated and attenuated. For example, Zeng et al. (2019) noted that the cumulative precipitation over a longer period of time prior to the observation controls SM. This justifies that the daily sum of precipitation (*Precipitation*) is less likely to be a strong predictor for SM. The generally lower importance associated with the climatic variables (e.g., seasonal variation in evapotranspiration) is likely caused by the redundancy in information of correlated features with higher importance such as *Day of the year* (Figure S10). The importance of temporal variables, such as the *Day of the year* for SM predictions is in line with the previous study by Q. Li et al. (2022). The importance of the hydroclimatic predictors might be higher across sites with different hydroclimatic forcing, while the *Day of the year* seems to be a good proxy for seasonal hydroclimatic variability in case of similar climatic forcings as on the studied hillslope.

FIGURE 5 Feature importance across machine learning (ML) methods for training and test datasets (training-test split 5) as boxplots for the shuffling repetitions. The x -axis displays the reduction in R^2 associated with removing the respective feature from the model (for details, see Section 2.2.4). GBRT, gradient boosted regression trees; NN, neural network; RF, random forest; SVR, support vector regression.

The importance of *Elevation* (0.10–0.24 for the test sets of RF, GBRT, and NN) and *Slope* (0.07–0.10 for the test sets of SVR) is probably linked to their control of spatial SM variability related to the topographical effect on lateral water flow paths and their convergence across the landscape, in line with findings from Martini et al. (2017) and Takagi and Lin (2012). Also, Xie et al. (2020) remarked soil texture and terrain features as important SM predictors, although they noted the higher importance of climatic conditions, in agreement with our previous argument that *sine* and *cosine* of *Day of the year* incorporate climate forcings and thus may mask the importance of the climatic variables in our ML models. Hengl et al.

(2018) report that using coordinates as spatial predictors can serve as a measure to represent the spatial autocorrelation of a target variable. For instance, geostatistical interpolation methods strongly rely on spatial autocorrelation. In our study, the y coordinate represents the north-south direction, the main axis of topographical variability along the hillslope. The importance of coordinates and the spatial predictors *Soil Porosity*, *Elevation*, and *Slope* differs across individual models. Here, the importance patterns of RF and GBRT (*Elevation*: 0.0–0.22 and *Soil Porosity*: 0.06–0.12 values for test sets) are more comparable than with SVR (*Elevation*: 0.01, *Soil Porosity*: 0.11–0.12, and *Slope*: 0.5–0.09; values for test sets) or NN

(*Elevation*: 0.11–0.13, *Soil Porosity*: 0.33–0.35, and *Slope*: 0.01; values for test sets), or both SVR and NN, possibly due to a similar architecture of RF and GBRT. This also reflects the similar performance of both models.

To conclude from the feature importance analysis, a set of major features (*Day of the year*, *Depth of Sensor*, *Soil Porosity*, and *Elevation*) crystallized as most important. Thus, these features proved to be suitable to describe SM variations and we think they are worth being included in further SM studies and prediction models. Additionally, we want to highlight the value of a feature importance analysis to understand the model functioning more profoundly and thus recommend to always include it, especially when applying different ML methods.

3.3 | Predicted soil moisture maps

For each daily time stamp in the considered period (September 15, 2012 till November 14, 2013), SM maps of the study site were predicted by models trained on training-test split five. The predicted maps for the selected dates (February 16, 2013, and July 16, 2013) and corresponding animations combining map predictions for all dates are available on Zenodo (Houben, Ebeling, et al., 2025). The generated SM maps considered the spatiotemporal variations in the SM observations. All ML methods were able to depict the seasonal variation in SM, with SM in spring and winter being generally higher than in summer and autumn, as expected following the typical seasonal pattern represented in the SM measurements (Figure 1; Figure S1; Table S7).

Areas with high SM close to the stream and to the south of the stream in all seasons except autumn were only poorly predicted by the ML models (Table S7). In these areas, the average absolute error between observation and prediction exceeded $0.02 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^3$, a value that is reported as a reasonable instrument error (Qu et al., 2016). Largely, all models underestimated SM at the deepest soil depth and near the stream (Table S7). The difference in performance in areas close to and south of the stream could be the result of the higher importance of *Slope* in SVR predictions, while *Elevation* was more important than the *Slope* in the RF and GBRT models (Figure 5). Also, other studies report an imbalance of errors in spatial SM predictions, which resulted in regions where SM is systematically under- or overestimated (Xie et al., 2020; Zeng et al., 2019). The underestimation of SM in deeper soil layers may result from the fact that important features such as *Day of the year* might have less predictive capacity at deeper layers as the relationship of SM at deeper layers to climatic forcing is attenuated. For instance, seasonal variations in observed SM declined with increasing soil depth (Figure S1). Similarly, Zeng et al. (2019) noticed a decrease in the importance of climatic features and a drop in the accuracy of SM predictions with increasing depth. The above-described spatiotemporal

patterns in the predictions of the models are further visible in the prediction maps in Figure 6, created for an exemplary day during the wet (February 16, 2013) and dry period (July 16, 2013).

3.4 | Handling of models

RF and GBRT can be set up and parameterized easily since the number of tuning parameters is comparably low and, therefore, the search space for tuning remains quite narrow compared to NN and SVR. This also translates into a lower computational burden for training RF and GBRT models. We had to spend much more effort on parameter selection in order to obtain similar results with SVR and NN. SVR models were computationally intensive and did not achieve full convergence of any SVR model. All model parameters that were finally used for the training, test, and prediction are listed in Section S3.2 and Tables S3–S6.

The high number of parameters involved in NN translates into a large hyperparameter tuning space and computational burden for training. For NN, the network structure in terms of the number and size of hidden layers should be adequate for the dataset size as mentioned by Cai et al. (2019). For instance, Cai et al. (2019) evaluated a two-layer and a single-layer NN for temporal predictions of SM. Due to the prediction of a single SM time series (no spatial data) including training data of more than 2 years, their achieved performances were quite high ($R^2 > 0.7$ and $\text{RMSE} < 0.06 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^3$ for the single-layer NN, $R^2 > 0.9$ and $\text{RMSE} < 0.01 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^3$ for the two-layer NN). Their study highlighted the advantage to include more than a single hidden layer in an NN for SM prediction. We found the number and size of the hidden layers hard to define a priori but obtained the highest performance with only two hidden layers and decreasing number of nodes toward the output layer. Overall, training the NN proved to be difficult, given the extensive number of hyperparameters which influence aspects of a NN such as the model's architecture (number of neurons and layers in the network), the convergence behavior of the training process and the generalization of the final model to new and unseen data. The choice of these parameters had a remarkable impact on the training duration as well as the required computational resources.

In general, starting spatiotemporal SM predictions with RF and GBRT models by using the default parameters and recommendation given in the scikit-learn package (Pedregosa et al., 2011) that is accessed via our SM module seems to be a suitable option. With the provided Python SM module, a basis for conducting SM predictions using ML was built. Additional methods present in the scikit-learn package (Pedregosa et al., 2011) can be easily applied and explored. Moreover, the SM module can be used to train machine-learning models with any SM data including remote sensing-derived

FIGURE 6 Maps of predicted daily mean soil moisture for a wet day in February (a) and a dry day in July (b) across machine learning (ML) methods (training-test split 5) and for three different depths (0.05, 0.25, and 0.50 m). Circles represent the actual soil moisture readings at the sensor locations. The domain size is approximately 80 m × 250 m. GBRT, gradient boosted regression trees; NN, neural network; RF, random forest; SVR, support vector regression.

SM data. For this, values of the features can easily be exchanged for another field site, non-available features can be removed, additional features can be added (from field measurements or remote sensing including satellite observations), and the target variable can be adapted (SM field measurements or remote sensing).

4 | CONCLUSIONS

We predicted SM in a grassland hillslope in a small agricultural catchment across space and time. Predictions were based on daily SM measurements over 14 months from 40 sensor locations across three different depths, auxiliary feature data,

and four different ML methods. The model performances and feature importance were assessed and predictions for selected models were mapped. The developed workflow was implemented as a Python module, which we provide here for further applications.

Generally, the model performances ($R^2 = 0.28\text{--}0.66$, $RMSE = 0.06\text{--}0.10$) were in a similar magnitude to what has been reported for spatial and spatiotemporal SM predictions in previous studies using kriging and other ML methods. Performances varied with ML methods but even more strongly with the spatial split of training and test data. Therefore, it is important to be aware of the large variability in model performances caused by high spatial heterogeneity in SM and potentially resulting imbalances of

SM values in training–test splits. The *Day of the year* emerged as an important feature to predict SM and thus can serve as a proxy to represent seasonal hydroclimatic variability. The depth of sensor, porosity, and elevation allow to represent of spatial variability and depth-wise attenuation of the SM. Despite variations in predictive performance, the tree-based methods RF and GBRT performed best on average and are rather easy to parametrize.

Therefore, future research should prioritize comparative studies of multiple ML methods on specific datasets, with an emphasis on including RF and/or GBRT. For the prediction of spatially heterogeneous variables such as SM, it is crucial to consider several spatial splits of training and test data as well as to assess the importance of model input data. The development of our module marks a key step toward reproducible scientific results, since it allows an easy application to future studies, including different features and target variables, as well as the use of other ML methods. We, therefore, encourage the use of this module as a foundation for further research and to develop SM prediction tools for practitioners in agriculture, forestry, landscaping and environmental management.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Timo Houben: Conceptualization; data curation; formal analysis; investigation; methodology; project administration; software; validation; visualization; writing—original draft. **Pia Ebeling:** Conceptualization; data curation; formal analysis; investigation; methodology; software; validation; visualization; writing—original draft. **Swamini Khurana:** Conceptualization; data curation; formal analysis; investigation; methodology; project administration; software; validation; visualization; writing—original draft. **Julia Sabine Schmid:** Conceptualization; data curation; formal analysis; investigation; methodology; software; validation; visualization; writing—original draft. **Johannes Boog:** Conceptualization; data curation; formal analysis; investigation; methodology; software; validation; visualization; writing—original draft.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available on Zenodo (Houben, Ebeling, et al., 2025). The soil moisture prediction module is available on GitHub (<https://github.com/timohouben/sm-module>) and is referenced via Zenodo (Houben, Boog, et al., 2025).

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

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